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List of Acronyms

BGO	Bismuth Germanate
CIR	Corotating Interaction Regions
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CUSUM	Cumulative Sum
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument (on-board SOHO)
ESP	Energetic Storm Particles
FD	Forbush Decrease
FM	Failure Mode
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	Geometry and Tracking (Monte-Carlo simulation toolkit)
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement (of cosmic rays)
HET	High Energy Telescope
HMF	Heliospheric Magnetic Field
HXR	Hard X-Ray
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
khp	Keyhole Period
MIP	Minimum Ionizing Particle
PHA	Pulse Height Analysis
RHESSI	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager
SC	Solar Cycle
SEE	Solar Energetic Electron
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector
WP	Work Package
SWA	Solar Wind Analyser
FMO	Flight Model
EPD	Energetic Particle Detector
FD	Forbush Decrease
EPT	Electron Proton Telescope
SIS	SupraThermal Ion Spectrograph
ESA	European Space Agency

STEP	SupraThermal Electrons and Protons
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COSPIN	COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
HET	High Energy Telescope
IMF	Interplanetary Magnetic Field
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
SEE	Solar Energetic Electron
SC	Solar Cycle
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
D	Deliverable
ML	Machine Learning
TSF	Time Series Forest
STSF	Supervised Time Series Forest
BOSS	Bag of SFA Symbols

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the first results from a systematic analysis of the [SOHO / EPHIN](#), [SoLO / HET](#) and [Ulysses / KET](#) measurements. The analysis has resulted in the creation of multiple catalogs of (ultra) relativistic Solar Energetic Electron ([SEE](#)) events, covering different regions and time periods. Specifically, these include events observed: (a) at 1 AU from 1995 to 2017; (b) at various radial distances along the Ulysses trajectory from 1990 to 2006, and (c) at 0.3–1 AU along the SoLO trajectory from 2020 to 2023. The latter will further pertain to the ongoing solar cycle 25. This document represents the second deliverable of Work Package ([WP](#))5 within the [SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data \(SPEARHEAD\)](#) project, which is funded by the Horizon Europe framework program of the European Union (EU). The compiled 1 AU, Ulysses, and SoLO catalogs are based on the scanning of electron energies of ~ 5 MeV, ~ 1 MeV, and ≥ 5 MeV, respectively, as measured by [SOHO / EPHIN](#), Ulysses, and SoLO. In total, 254 energetic electron events have been identified. The current document outlines the methodologies applied in identifying SEE events and characterizing their properties. Additionally, it presents the full catalog and provides a detailed discussion of its key outputs.

1 Introduction

In contrast to protons with an energy above 100 MeV that originate from the slowly varying Galactic Cosmic Ray (GCR) background, from Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) and Energetic Storm Particles (ESP) events, high-energy electrons with energies beyond several MeV have additional sources. In particular, planetary sources like Jupiter serve as a significant contributor of these energetic electrons. Moreover, the flux of these high-energy electrons exhibit complex and dynamic variations, driven by propagation processes within the heliosphere, influenced by solar activity and the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF).

1.1 MeV electron population in the Earth vicinity

The population of MeV electrons in interplanetary (IP) space is influenced by multiple sources, including SEP events, GCRs, and Jupiter's magnetosphere. Solar flares and eventually Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) accelerate electrons through magnetic reconnection and shock acceleration, injecting them into the heliosphere. Additionally, Jupiter serves as a quasi-continuous source of energetic electrons, particularly at energies up to a few tenth of MeV, as its powerful magnetosphere efficiently accelerates and releases electrons into IP space. These Jovian electrons propagate outward along the Interplanetary Magnetic Field (IMF) (Bolton et al. 2015).

Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs): GCRs originate outside the solar system and contribute to the population of high-energy electrons. Their flux at Earth is modulated by solar activity and the heliospheric magnetic field (Potgieter 2018). Short term variations are associated to Forbush Decreases (FDs) (see for a review Cane 2000, and references therein). The measured amplitude is of the order of a few ten percent (see Aguilar et al. 2021, 2022, and references therein) at energies above 1 GeV.

Jovian Electrons, originating from Jupiter's magnetosphere, significantly contribute to the population of MeV electrons near Earth's orbit (e.g. Cooper et al. 1991; Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2000; Casolino et al. 2007, and references therein). Jupiter's strong magnetic field and its interaction with the solar wind create a powerful magnetosphere that acts as a source of energetic electrons (see for example Dunn et al. 2024, and references therein). These electrons escape Jupiter's magnetosphere and propagate through interplanetary space, following the large-scale structure of the IMF (see for example Chenette et al. 1977; Vogt et al. 2020, and references therein). The Parker spiral configuration of the IMF plays a key role in channeling these electrons towards Earth (Dwyer et al. 1997; Vogt et al. 2013; Kühl et al. 2013). Figure 1 (left panel) shows the magnetic connectivity of the Earth to Jupiter with a region marked by shading for which Jovian electrons can only reach the Earth via transport perpendicular to the IMF, adapted from Kühl et al. (2013). In addition, the figure contains two Parker spirals with a solar wind velocity of 300 km/s and 800 km/s, respectively, showing the broad range in connectivity to Jupiter for an observer close to Earth. Jovian electron events as shown in Fig. 1 (right panel) are characterized by the detection of energetic electrons originating from Jupiter's magnetosphere and arriving at Earth. These events have been observed since the early days of space-based particle measurements and are notable for their distinct periodicity, energy spectra, and dependence on solar wind structures (Simnett et al. 1977; Moses 1987).

SEP events Solar flares and CMEs are primary contributors to > 100 MeV/amu ions and electrons. The acceleration processes of suprathermal and near- to relativistic electrons in the solar corona and its correlation to measurements in interplanetary space has been investigated by several authors:

Magnetic Reconnection: Magnetic reconnection is a fundamental process in solar flares where oppositely directed magnetic fields converge, break, and reconnect. This reconfiguration releases substantial energy, accelerating electrons to high velocities (energies). Observations and simulations have demonstrated that electrons can be accelerated both at the reconnection site and within

Figure 1: Polar coordinate system co-rotating with Jupiter. Besides the orbits of the Earth and Jupiter, two Parker spirals of different velocity connecting the Sun with Jupiter are plotted. In addition, radial lines indicate the intersection of Parker spirals of different velocities with the Earth's orbit. The region where Jovian electrons can reach the Earth only by perpendicular diffusion is shaded.

the outflowing plasma jets, known as reconnection exhausts (see for example [Zhou et al. 2021](#), and references therein).

Stochastic Acceleration: In the turbulent environment of a solar flare, electrons gain energy through interactions with randomly moving magnetic fields and plasma waves. This stochastic, or second-order Fermi, acceleration process contributes to the high-energy tail observed in electron energy distributions during flares (see for example [Fletcher et al. 2011](#), and references therein).

Shock Acceleration: Shock waves generated by rapid plasma motions in flares can accelerate electrons via the first-order Fermi mechanism. As electrons cross the shock front multiple times, they gain energy, leading to the production of high-energy SEPs (see for example [Li et al. 2022](#), and references therein).

[Krucker et al. \(2007\)](#) laid the foundation for understanding the correlation between Hard X-Ray (HXR) photon spectra observed by Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI) and in-situ electron spectra measured near Earth. Confirmed by [Dresing et al. \(2021\)](#) they identified a positive correlation between the spectral indices of HXR emissions and interplanetary electrons, suggesting a common acceleration mechanism at the Sun.

The transport of high-energy electrons within the heliosphere is influenced by several factors:

Heliospheric Magnetic Field (HMF): The HMF “dictates” the guiding paths of charged particles. Variations due to solar wind fluctuations impact electron transport ([Boschini et al. 2018](#)).

Magnetic Turbulence: Scattering due to turbulent magnetic fields alters electron diffusion rates.

Solar Wind Conditions: The speed and density of the solar wind influence electron convection and diffusion, with high-speed solar wind streams enhancing transport.

1.2 Discrimination of Jovian and SEP events

Jovian electron events and SEP events both result in increases of MeV electrons in interplanetary space. However, they originate from different sources and have distinct characteristics (Mitchell et al. 2022; Vogt et al. 2018). Differentiating between these two types of electron enhancements is crucial for this deliverable.

Temporal Characteristics Jovian electron events exhibit a 13-month periodicity (as observed at Earth or near 1 AU), corresponding to Jupiter’s synodic period, due to varying magnetic connectivity through the HMF. These enhancements occur in 4-8 month cycles with modulations driven by Corotating Interaction Regions (CIRs) (Dunzlaff 2018). In contrast, SEP events are associated with specific solar phenomena and do not follow a regular periodic pattern (Reames 1999, 2025).

Energy Spectra The energy spectra of Jovian electron events typically follow power-law distributions with spectral indices in the range of 1.4-2 at energies below 15 MeV (Mitchell et al. 2022). SEP events, on the other hand, exhibit broader spectral variations depending on the acceleration mechanisms involved in the solar event (Reames 1999, 2025).

Radio Emissions Jovian electron events are linked to Jupiter’s radio emissions, which can serve as indicators of electron acceleration within Jupiter’s magnetosphere (Vogt et al. 2018). SEP events are often associated with solar radio bursts, such as type II and III bursts, which indicate shock-driven and flare-accelerated particle populations (Reames 1999, 2025).

Proton Flux and Proton-to-Electron Ratio A key distinction between these events is the presence of protons:

Jovian electron events are **not** accompanied by significant increases in proton flux. The proton-to-electron ratio remains low.

SEP events typically involve simultaneous increases in both electron and proton fluxes, with a higher proton-to-electron ratio (Cliver 2009; Kolympiris et al. 2023).

Figure 2: Both panels display three channels of $\approx 6 - 10$ MeV electrons observed by the Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) aboard Ulysses (presented as the blue, orange and green traces in each panel, respectively). The expectation is that increases in the electron count rates due to solar events are accompanied by strong increases in the 30 to 120 MeV proton count rates (P32; black trace) as shown in the right panel. Therefore, the ~ 30 MeV proton channel is required to exceed a threshold similarly to the ones measured in the three electron sub-channels, in order for an SEE to be marked.

As an example Fig. 2 displays the identification of a Jovian electron event (panel on the left hand side) versus a Solar Energetic Electron (SEE) event (panel on the right hand side) in Ulysses measurements.

The black trace (P32) in both panels depicts protons, while the electron recordings (E12) are presented in orange, blue and green color. As can be seen in the case of the SEE there is a clear enhancement in electrons and a simultaneous increase in protons. Contrary in the case of Jovian electrons, although an increase in electrons is clearly seen, protons are decaying, signifying their non-solar origin. The identification of electron events is discussed in detail in Section 3.1. As a note, many of the SEE candidate events were not due to solar electrons but rather due to Jovian ones.

Temporal Profiles of Proton and Electron Fluxes Jovian electron events have gradual intensity increases with extended durations, reflecting the continuous nature of electron release from Jupiter's magnetosphere (Dunzlaff 2018). SEP events, in contrast, are characterized by impulsive, rapid onset phases followed by a decay, mirroring the dynamics of solar eruptions Reames (1999).

Short term increases of the electron flux are caused by SEE and Jovian electrons. In order to separate SEE from the Jovian electron events, the temporal profiles of the high energy electrons need to be compared with those of protons at about 30 MeV. Therefore, only electron events with proton flux increases are taken into account.

2 Data and Instrumentation

Here we utilize energetic particle measurements taken by three space missions: Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO), Solar Orbiter (SoIO) and Ulysses. In order to cover the energy range from a few MeV to above 50 MeV for electrons we use the Electron Proton Helium Instrument (EPHIN) aboard SOHO (subsection 2.1), the High Energy Telescope (HET) aboard SoIO and the KET aboard Ulysses.

2.1 SOHO / EPHIN

Figure 3: On the left a sketch of the Electron Proton Helium Instrument (EPHIN) sensor is given with the 6 Solid State Detectors (SSDs) marked by A to F and the anticoincidence cylinder as G. The two SSDs A and B have six sectors with the inner sector 0 and a ring consisting of sector 1 to 5 (see lower right panel). The upper left shows a photo of the flight unit of EPHIN.

Instrument description

The Electron Proton Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) onboard the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) was launched in December 1995 and orbits around the Lagrangian point L1. Figure 3 shows a sketch and a photograph of the instrument on the left and right, respectively. It

consists of six SSDs (labeled A - F in Fig. 3) enclosed in a scintillator (G) that acts as an anticoincidence. The two SSDs A and B have six sectors with the inner sector 0 and a ring consisting of sector 1 to 5 (see lower right panel). The sectors are used to determine the direction of the incoming particle with higher precision and to reduce the instrument dead time during periods of high particle fluxes as explained in Kühl et al. (2020).

In 1997 and 2017, EPHIN was switched to failure modes E and D, respectively. This means that detectors D and E are excluded from any coincidence logic due to the increased noise levels in these detectors. Due to the loss of the two detectors the original Level-2 proton and helium channels listed in Tab. 1 have been successfully replaced by a Level-3 data set (see for details Kühl et al. 2020; Kühl & Heber 2019; Kühl et al. 2017, and references therein). Note, that due to the definition of the coincidence channels - defined by the number of detectors that the particles passes and by the energy loss in SSD A - the Level 2 data can only be used for the investigation of electrons and the integral channel. However, as explained below the Level-2 electron data need to be used with caution and a new Level-3 product will replace the old Level-2 files for electrons and the integral channel too. In contrast to ions for which the full

Table 1: EPHIN energy channels and coincidence conditions (from Müller-Mellin et al. 1995).

Type	Name	Energy Range	M ¹	P ²	Coincidence Condition ³
Electron	E150	0.25 – 0.70 MeV	1	4	A0 $\overline{A1}$ B0 $\overline{C0}$ $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	E300	0.67 – 3.00 MeV	1	4	A0 $\overline{A1}$ B0 C0 $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	E1300	2.64 – 6.18 MeV	1	4	A0 $\overline{A1}$ B0 C0 D0 $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	E3000	4.80 – 10.4 MeV	1	4	A0 $\overline{A1}$ B0 C0 D0 E0 $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
Proton	P4	4.3 – 7.8 MeV	3	4	A1 $\overline{A4}$ B0 $\overline{C0}$ $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	P8	7.8 – 25.0 MeV	3	4	A1 $\overline{A3}$ B0 C0 $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	P25	25.0 – 40.9 MeV	3	4	A1 $\overline{A2}$ B0 C0 D0 $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	P41	40.9 – 53.0 MeV	3	4	A1 $\overline{A2}$ B0 C0 D0 E0 $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
Helium	H4	4.3 – 7.8 MeV/N	4	40	A4 B0 $\overline{C0}$ $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	H8	7.8 – 25.0 MeV/N	4	16	A3 B0 C0 $\overline{D0}$ $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	H25	25.0 – 40.9 MeV/N	4	4	A2 B0 C0 D0 $\overline{E0}$ $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
	H41	40.9 – 53.0 MeV/N	4	4	A2 B0 C0 D0 E0 $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
Integral		E > 8.70 MeV			
	INT	P > 53.0 MeV	1	0	A0 B0 C0 D0 E0 $\overline{F0}$ $\overline{G0}$
		H > 53.0 MeV/N			

¹Multiplicity ²Priority Buffer Depth ³Segment index for A and B detector not shown

Note:

- (i). 33 coincidence countrates + 17 single detector countrates + 6 calibration/control channels A0n B0n C0 D0 E0 F0 (n = 0...5), total of 56 counters
 (ii). thresholds: A0n = 30 keV B0n = 60 keV n = 0...5
 A1 = 270 keV C0 = 370 keV
 A2 = 970 keV D0 = 580 keV
 A3 = 2.1 MeV E0 = 580 keV
 A4 = 5.3 MeV F0 = 150 keV
 G0 = 100 keV

energy range coverage can be recovered using the energy loss ΔE in the different detectors for electron only two and one energy channel(s) remain for which a higher energy resolution can be obtained. The last channel, the energy loss for electrons in the detector without knowing in which detector the electron is stopping can not be used to obtain information on the primary electron energy. However, a data product for electrons covering the energy range up to about 1 MeV, i.e., electrons stopping in SSD B, has been developed and will be presented in an upcoming paper. However, the energy range towards the highest electron energies is substantial reduced when switching to Failure Modes (FMs) E and D. To quantify the effect the Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML) model of EPHIN (Köberle et al. 2024)

Figure 4: The left and right panel display the response functions of electrons in the different energy channels as defined in Tab. 1 for periods for which the outer segments are used (ring on) and for those when the outer segments are logically turned off (ring off). For details see Kühn et al. (2020) and the text.

has been used in GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT) 4 computations to determine the energy response of electrons with primary energies between 0.1 MeV to 30 MeV in the last coincidence channels for which the energy loss ΔE in SSD F is smaller than 150 keV. Following Sullivan (1971), we compute the corresponding energy responses that are shown in the left panel of Fig. 4 for the nominal electron channels (see Tab. 1 for the notation), E1300 FM E¹ in FM E, and E1300 FM E & D² in FM E & FM D. The whole process is detailed in Deliverable (D) 2.3. The right panel differs from the left one, that the outer ring segments are switched off, so that the response is about 20 times lower than the one with the ring segments used. Important for this deliverable are the fluxes of electrons with efficient energies of about 5 MeV. However, comparing the energy response of E3000, E1300 FM E and E1300 FM E & D it can be found that the lower energy threshold decreases from about 4 MeV to 2.5 MeV to below 1 MeV, respectively. This behavior is expected because of the combination of channels E1300 and E3000 and E300, E1300 and E3000 into one channel E1300 FM E and E1300 FM E & D, respectively.

Like for the penetrating protons and single detectors, the efficient energy and geometric factor of the electron channels depend strongly on the input spectra. For electrons the spectra in the energy range of interest can be approximated by power laws $\Phi(E) = \Phi_0 \cdot \left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)^{-\gamma}$ with different values of γ . Heber et al. (2024) utilized the bow tie method in order to determine the above quantities. In Heber et al. (2024) the GCR spectrum is approximated by the solution of the Force Field approximation (for details of the equation and its derivation see Moraal 2013, and references therein). Note, that the efficient energy for GCRs ions is therefore much higher than the ones that should be used for SEP event analysis. For the ultra-relativistic SEP events even the standard values are not appropriate because of the soft energy spectra.

Because of the broad energy response of the electron channels the Bow Tie method is applied to the EPHIN channels utilizing power laws with γ varying between -4 and -2 to compute the efficient energy and response factor. The procedure is detailed in Fig. 5. The upper left panel shows the computed energy response function (see also right panel in Fig. 4). The upper right panel displays a series of power-law test spectra, $F(E, \gamma) = A \cdot E^{-\gamma}$ with γ adapted to the expected range of the spectral indices. Here the spectral range was chosen to be $\gamma = -4$ to $\gamma = -2$ in steps of 0.1. This gives us the energy-dependent count rate $C(E, \gamma)$ as

$$C(E, \gamma) = R(E) \cdot F(E, \gamma) \cdot \Delta E, \quad (1)$$

where ΔE is the bin width of the response function. This is shown in the lower left panel of Fig. 5.

We then sum over all energy bins E_i to obtain the total count rate of the channel:

$$C_{\text{chan}}(\gamma) = \sum_{i=0}^n C(E_i, \gamma), \quad (2)$$

¹With FM E no difference is made for particles stopping or penetrating SSD D

²If FM D is turned on in addition no differences are made for particles stopping or penetrating SSD C.

Figure 5: The top left panel presents the response function of E1300 FM E that is when FM E is turned on (see also the left panel of Fig. 4). The top right panel displays a set of power-law input spectra with a spectral index ranging from -4 to -2 in steps of 0.1. In the lower left and right panels, the channel count rates and the channel response factor, calculated using eq. 2 and 3, are plotted against energy. The effective energy E_{eff} and characteristic response R_{BT} are marked by a dotted, horizontal and vertical line in the lower right panel, respectively.

where n is the total number of bins in the response function $R(E)$. Next, a response factor R_{chan} is calculated that the channel must have in order to achieve the count rate C_{chan} , assuming that it only measures particles at a certain energy:

$$R_{\text{chan}}(E, \gamma) = \frac{C_{\text{chan}}(\gamma)}{F(E, \gamma)}, \quad (3)$$

The lower right panel of Fig. 5 shows the response factors from eq. 3, plotted against an energy interval E_{chan} from about 1 to 10 MeV. Each curve represents the results for a different spectral index γ . As can be seen, there is no single point where all the curves intersect, as would be the case for an ideal instrument. Therefore, we define the point at which the distance between all curves is minimal as the effective energy E_{eff} of this channel. These effective energies as well as the response factors are summarized in Tab. 2 for different channels:

Table 2: Energy response of the EPHIN electron channels computed using the GEANT 4 model provided by Köberle et al. (2024) and the computation script provided to the D2.3.

Coincidence	nominal Response	Response cuts	E_{eff} nom	E_{eff} cuts
E300	$6.33 \pm 7.03e-1$	$6.40 \pm 7.20e-1$	1.080	1.084
E300 ring off	$2.49e-1 \pm 2.87e-2$	$2.53e-1 \pm 2.99e-2$	1.080	1.084
E1300	$1.5e+1 \pm 1.24$	$1.47e+1 \pm 1.19$	3.506	3.506
E1300 ring off	$6.25e-1 \pm 5.42e-2$	$6.11e-1 \pm 4.99e-2$	3.506	3.506
E3000	$1.5e+1 \pm 1.24$	$1.47e+1 \pm 1.19$	6.39	
E3000 ring off	$6.25e-1 \pm 5.42e-2$	$6.11e-1 \pm 4.99e-2$	6.38	
E1300 FM E	$1.5e+1 \pm 1.24$	$1.47e+1 \pm 1.19$	3.780	3.850
E1300 FM E ring off	$6.25e-1 \pm 5.42e-2$	$6.11e-1 \pm 4.99e-2$	3.780	3.850
E300 FM E & D	$1.5e+1 \pm 1.24$	$1.47e+1 \pm 1.19$	1.15	1.15
E300 FM E & D ring off	$6.25e-1 \pm 5.42e-2$	$6.11e-1 \pm 4.99e-2$	1.15	1.15

Nominal mode: In the energy range from a few hundred keV to above 10 MeV three channels are available that have an efficient energy of about 1, 3.5, and 6.4 MeV, from which the last two are appropriate for the electron list. However, only one event was measured by SOHO / EPHIN in 1997.

Failure Mode (FM) E: From mid 1997 to September 2017 the instrument was set in FM E. From Tab. 2 only the last channel E1300 with an efficient energy $E_{eff} = 3.8$ MeV can be used in this deliverable (see also Fig. 4).

Failure Mode (FM) E, D: Since September 2017 the instrument was set in FM E and FM D. From Tab. 2 none of the remaining channels can be used here in our study.

As a result, only three out of four electron channels are available for the detection of stopping electrons from 1997 to 2017 when most of the SEE events occurred in Solar Cycles (SCs) 23 and 24. Table 2 summarizes the efficient energies of the different channels taking into account the FMs. The computation of the response functions shown in Fig. 4 are summarized in deliverable D2.3.

Figure 6: Measured flux of electrons by SOHO EPHIN in the E300 and E1300 channels (see for definition Tab. 1). The plot shows the time profiles during the SEP event from February 25, 2014. For details see text.

Contamination by photons The accuracy of the electron measurements is affected by high-energy electromagnetic radiation, primarily X-rays and gamma rays (Mann et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2021).

As illustrated in Fig. 6 a short increase in the electron channels is measured around 0:40 h of February 25 with the final electron increase about an hour later. The first increase can be attributed to the X-4 solar flare on February 25, 2014 occurring at about 0:41 h (for an extensive discussion see Sharykin et al. 2023, and references therein). The second increase belongs to the SEE arriving at about 2:00 UT. As will be discussed in D3.3, high energy photons interfere with SEP electron measurements through several mechanisms:

- **Photon Interactions:** High-energy photons can interact with detector materials, producing secondary electrons via the photoelectric effect and Compton scattering (Rodriguez-Pacheco et al. 2021).
- **Background Noise:** Gamma rays contribute to the background signal, making it difficult to distinguish true SEP electron events.
- **Instrument Saturation:** Intense solar X-ray bursts during flares can saturate detectors, leading to misinterpretation of SEP fluxes.

For SOHO EPHIN, X-ray and gamma-ray interference remains a significant contribution and challenge in characterizing the SEP electron measurements, i.e., the determination of the onset time of an event. This effect will be taken into account when discussing the methodology.

Contamination by protons: Sierks (1997) pointed out that the channel that measures electrons above 1 MeV is contaminated by electron signatures caused by γ -rays. Shown in the upper left and right panel of Fig. 7 are the 2-dimensional histograms of the energy loss in SSD B versus the one in SSD C and in acSSD C versus the one in SSD D for the electron channel E1300 FM E as defined in Tab. 1. In that case SSD C is the last detector for which particles are penetrating. These distributions are shown in the upper and lower left panel in Fig. 7 for a quiet time period from January 1 to January 27, 2007 and from July 14 to July 18, 2000, respectively. The distributions shown in the left lower corner is caused by Minimum Ionizing Particles (MIPs), here electrons. Protons that are counted as MIPs need to penetrate the full sensor and therefore would lead to signals either in SSD F and/or detector G that act as anticoincidence and are not expected to contribute to this part of the distribution.

Figure 7: Two-dimensional energy loss distributions in SSD B versus SSD C and SSD C versus SSD D for the first 27 days in 2007 in the upper row and from July 14 to July 18, 2000 during the Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) 59 in the lower row for the electron channel E1300 in the left and right panel, respectively (for details on the channels see Tab. 1). Further details are discussed in the text.

Following Sierks (1997) the second distribution located around the double energy loss of the MIP distribution is caused by two electron signals that are caused by pair production of γ -particles. This is seen only during quiet times. The reason is that high energy protons above 300 MeV produce π^0 (Norbury 2009) that decay into two photons leading to the double MIP energy losses. For SEP events this is not relevant because low energy protons dominate the proton contamination. The characteristic track of protons can be identified in the SSD C versus D distribution (see right panels of Fig. 9). With increasing proton energy, the energy loss in SSD D is increasing and decreasing when the proton penetrates the SSD. For SSD C the energy loss is decreasing continuously. The main track stops when the particle penetrates the sensor at energies of about 80 MeV. However, a few entries are found that are most probably caused by higher energy protons. The splitting of the proton curves in the SSD B versus C distribution is caused by the same energy loss in SSD C for proton stopping and penetrating SSD D,

respectively.

The proton contamination looks different for the quiet time periods as shown in the upper right panel of Fig. 7. Here the proton track continues to higher energies and a second track becomes visible that can be attributed to backward penetrating protons indicating some inefficiency of the anti-coincidence. However, it is important to note that the contribution to MIP energies which we account to the distribution caused by electrons is negligible.

Figure 8: Count rates of the E150 and the P4GM coincidence counters (see Tab. 1) during a ring switch of the instrument. The P4GM is the part of the P4 that counts the entries in the inner segments only. For details see text.

Ring-Switch: One caveat of the EPHIN is the adaptable geometric factor. If the count rate in the inner segment of the first detector exceeds a certain threshold, the ring segments of SSD A and B are logically deactivated. The effect on the particle identification is shown in Fig. 9. In the moment the ring segments are switched off the geometric factor decreases by a factor of approximately 25, leading to a corresponding reduction in the count rate. This effect is shown in the left and right panel of Fig. 4 summarized in Tab. 2. In order to validate the computation, the ring segments were switched off during quiet times. The result is shown in Fig. 8. The count rate of the E150 channel is shown by the darker blue curve that decreases as expected when the ring is switched off. In contrast, the P4GM channel (light blue curve), which is the part of the P4 channel that utilizes the inner segments only, exhibits the opposite behavior. Its count rate increases when the ring is turned off and decreases when the ring is turned back on. This behavior is unexpected, as this channel only collects particles that pass through both the middle segments of the A and B detectors and should therefore be constant.

In order to understand the effect better we show in Fig. 9 left and right panel the energy loss distribution of SSD C versus SSD D with the ring segments on and off during GLE 59 from July 14 to July 18, 2000, respectively. The left panel corresponds to the lower right panel of Fig. 7 and has been repeated to compare both measurements with and without using the information from the ring segments. In both panels the track of protons stopping in and with increasing energy penetrating SSD D for energy losses in SSD C is clearly visible, indicating the identification of electrons and protons by using the energy loss in SSD A only has its disadvantage. However, during the ring off time, additional entries appear in both the electron and proton regime. These additional entries are most likely caused by a random coincidence: a particle entering the instrument through the switched-off outer ring of SSD A and hitting the inner segment of SSD B, combined with either a noise peak or another particle triggering the middle segment of SSD A. The additional proton and electron entries are most likely caused by a random coincidence between an electron triggering SSD A and a proton hitting SSD B. This means that the electron coincidence channels can get contaminated by protons but also the proton channels by electrons.

Comparing the left and right panels, the effect is not negligible since the proton contribution is obviously much larger than the electron one during the ring off period. Since the effect is so severe the electron channel needs to be corrected using energy loss information:

Figure 9: Shown here are the 2-dimensional energy loss distributions of the energy loss in **SSD-C** versus **SSD D** from July 14 to July 20, 2000 during the Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) 59 (see for example [Moraal & McCracken 2012](#); [Mishev & Usoskin 2016](#), and references to it) for the electron channel E1300 when all sectors of **SSD A** and **B** are used (ring on) and when only the inner segments are utilized (ring off, for details on the channels see Tab. 1). Further details are discussed in the text.

SSD A: A simple cutoff is applied to **SSD A** only.

SSD B and SSD C: The left panels of Fig. 9 show that the electron distribution in the matrix is well separated from the proton track and the two **MIP** distributions. A simple criteria is:

$$\Delta E_{SSD-B} \leq 250 \text{ keV} - \frac{\Delta E_{SSD C}}{10} \quad (4)$$

The influence of the cut is shown in the two left panels of Fig. 10. Note that due to the low noise level of **SSD B** and the lower flux of particles reaching the detector the number of spurious coincidences are much smaller than for **SSD A**.

SSD D: In **SSD D** energy losses of $\Delta E \leq 8000$ keV are taken into account. This is not shown in the right panels of Fig. 10.

As an example Fig. 11 shows the corrected and uncorrected flux measured in the E300 (orange and blue curves) and E1300 (red and green curves) channels during the January 7, 2014 **SEP** event. From the figure it is evident that the time profile of corrected and uncorrected fluxes can differ from each other significantly and that during this event only 15% of the entries in the E1300 channel are identified as electrons. Thus, in order to use electron fluxes from **EPHIN** in scientific studies these corrections need to be applied.

SOHO EPHIN electron channels show (strong) contamination of energetic protons. This is especially true when the ring segments are switched off. Thus a method based on the energy loss distributions in the SSDs has been developed and successfully applied to the measurements. However, it becomes evident that for scientific studies proton contamination corrections need to be applied.

Figure 10: Energy loss ΔE distribution of **SSD B** versus **SSD C** and **SSD C** versus **SSD D** are shown in the left and right panel. The upper and lower panels display the distributions without cuts and with cuts, respectively. For details see text.

Figure 11: Corrected and uncorrected fluxes of the E300 (orange and blue curves) and E1300 (red and green curves) channels as defined in Tab. 1 during the January 7, 2014 **SEP** event. The proton contamination during this event is significant and only about 15% of all entries in the E1300 are electrons. For details see text.

Geometric factor during ring off periods: There are also random coincidences involving electrons with other electrons. These electrons cannot be distinguished from normal electron coincidences, i.e., electrons traversing SSD A detector and stopping in SSD B. This means that we underestimate the response for electrons when the ring is switched off and as a result the calculated fluxes are too high.

To correct for this, we estimate the number of random coincidences caused by electrons entering through the outer ring of detector A using:

$$R = 2 \cdot n_A \cdot n_B \cdot \tau, \quad (5)$$

where n_A represents the count rate caused by noise or particles triggering only the middle segment of detector A (A_0) without triggering the B detector, $A_0\bar{B}_0$. Since the instrument data does not directly provide this information, we approximate n_A using the count rate in A_0 . This approximation is reasonable because, during an event, the count rate in A_0 is more than 20 times higher than the count rate in the middle segment of the B detector (B_0). Similarly, n_B represents the count rate in B_0 caused only by particles entering through the outer ring of detector A, $B_0\bar{A}_0$. The instrument does not provide this information because the outer ring is electrically turned off, so we estimate n_B by multiplying the B_0 count rate by 5/6. This factor arises from the ratio of the geometric factors for particles entering through the ring of A and hitting B_0 to those entering through any segment of A and hitting B_0 .

The duration of the coincidence window of the digital electronics is represented by τ . This approximation is based on the condition that the particle events follow a Poisson distribution and that $n_{1,2} \cdot \tau \ll 1$. The result of eq. 5 represents the number of random coincidences, which is distributed across all penetration depths. To estimate the number of random coincidences, we scale this value by the ratio of the counts in the AB coincidences (C_{AB}) to the total coincidence counts (C_{all}).

$$R_{AB} = R \frac{C_{AB}}{C_{all}} \quad (6)$$

With eq. 6 the fluxes in the histogram channels (F_{unc}) can be corrected with

$$F_{corr} = \frac{C_{AB} - R_{AB}}{C_{AB}} \cdot F_{unc} = \left(1 - \frac{R}{C_{all}}\right) \cdot F_{unc} \quad (7)$$

With this correction, the average "jump-height" is reduced from approximately 50% to around 20%, indicating that the correction method cannot correct the whole contamination in the channels during times when the ring is switched off.

During the so called ring off periods EPHIN coincidence channels have larger geometric factors due to random coincidences. A method to take this effect into account has been developed and successfully applied to the measurements.

Figure 12: Examples of a “keyhole period” (*khp*). See text for details.

Keyhole Periods (*khrs*) Another impact on the data coverage is due to **SOHO** keyhole periods: **SOHO** keyhole periods are specific times when the **SOHO** spacecraft experiences interruptions or limitations in its operations due to the alignment of the antenna to Earth. These periods typically last a few days to a couple of weeks. During keyhole periods, data transmission is reduced or even corrupted. They occur at predictable intervals, generally once or twice a year, depending on the spacecraft’s orbital dynamics and the relative positions of Earth, **SOHO**, and the Sun. European Space Agency (**ESA**)’s Science & Technology website provides updates and resources related to **SOHO**’s keyhole operations, offering insights into how these periods are managed and their impact on the mission https://soho.nascom.nasa.gov/hotshots/2004_01_04/. The impact of such a keyhole period was observed, for example, during the September 19, 2004 **SEP** event (Fig. 12). The figure shows the electron fluxes during the periods with a *khp* during the onset, maximum and the declining phase of the event. These periods are marked by *khp* in the catalogue.

2.2 SoIo / HET

SoIo is an ESA mission with an orbit that will take it both close to the Sun and to high latitudes. Among other instruments, it carries a magnetometer (Horbury et al. 2020) and Solar Wind Analyser (SWA) (Owen et al. 2020) to measure in situ magnetic field and plasma properties, as well as the Energetic Particle Detector (EPD) (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020) to measure suprathermal and energetic particles. Of particular interest is the HET instrument as part of the EPDs suite, a particle telescope covering the high-energy end of the energetic particle spectrum, as well as SEPs, which was found to be suitable to observe FDs (Freiherr von Forstner et al. 2021).

2.2.1 The HET Instrument

HET was designed to cover the high energy range for electrons, protons and also for several heavy ion species from $E \approx 7$ MeV/nuc to $E \approx 500$ MeV/nuc for ions that stop in the sensor head (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020). Two Electron Proton Telescope (EPT)-HET units, Flight Model (FMO)1 and FMO2, are mounted on the Solar Orbiter spacecraft with FMO1 looking in sun/antisun direction along the average Parker spiral and FMO2 pointing out of the ecliptic. The location of these units is illustrated in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Location of the EPD instruments on the SoIo spacecraft. The X-axis of the coordinate system points towards the Sun. On the left hand side the -Y panel of the spacecraft is shown with the SupraThermal Ion Spectrograph (SIS), SupraThermal Electrons and Protons (STEP) and EPT-HET FMO1 units. On the +Y side (right figure) only the EPT - HET FMO2 is located

Each HET instrument consists of 4 SSDs of $300 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, which are symmetrically arranged around a Bismuth Germanate (BGO) scintillation detector that allows particles to be detected from two directions. The entrance SSDs, named HET-A, feature two segments, while the two inner SSDs, named HET-B, feature three segments. Segmentation enables an adjustment of the geometric factors as well as a trajectory analysis of detected particles. The outermost segment of the HET-B detectors is used as a guard ring. Particles passing through this segment do not enter the instrument through the entrance window or are scattered inside the telescope and thus are neglected. In order to stop highly energetic heavy particles and thus achieve the required energy range, BGO was chosen as the scintillation material for the HET-C detector. The scintillation crystal is hexagonal with a thickness and edge length of 2 cm whose scintillation light is read out by two photodiodes placed on opposing sides (see Eftmann (2020))

Figure 14: Schematic diagram of the HET sensor head. Exemplary particle trajectories ending up in different data products are shown by the arrows: stopping in B (red), stopping in C (green), penetrating (blue), GCR channel (aquamarine), C single counter (orange). From (Freiherr von Forstner et al. 2021)

for further details).

2.2.2 Electron measurements with HET

Figure 14 shows a sketch of the HET instrument with exemplary particle trajectories for different coincidence conditions. There are four nominal electron channels for HET, one stopping in B with energies between 0.2 and 1 MeV (red) and three channels stopping in C with energies between 0.8 and 15.3 MeV (green) (Fleth et al. 2023).

In this study, a combination of the channel of electrons stopping in B and the lowest channel of electrons stopping in C with energies around 1 MeV is considered, as well as the highest energetic channels of electrons stopping in C with energies between 5 and 15 MeV. Two major patches were introduced during the mission lifetime on October 12th, 2021 and on April 16th, 2024 to improve and thereby altering the electron measurements. The rationale behind these two patches is highlighted in Fig.15.

Patch 1 October 12th, 2021 lower energy channel

The left panel of Fig.15 shows a 2-D histogram of energy deposits in A+B vs. C for measurements taken between March 2020 and October 2021 by the HET FMO1. The red curves mark the limits of the three individual channels for electrons stopping in C. Fleth et al. (2023) identified two populations of particles not related to electrons. Population A, which dominates the counts observed in the lowest channel (E800) with energy losses in $C < 1$ MeV, has been found to be caused by electronic noise from the signal in C, which has not been correctly characterized and considered in the trigger logic of the instrument. Electrons stopping in B were therefore falsely identified as stopping in C simply due to noise, and the counts of the flux of the E200 electron channel were underestimated, while the flux in the E800 channel was overestimated. Therefore, an absolute threshold of 1 MeV (marked as orange vertical line) was introduced for particles stopping in C with the first patch, resulting in a cleaned E800 channel, as well as an increase in flux for the lowest channel of electrons stopping in B, as can be seen as discontinuity in Fig. 22.

Population B was identified to be caused by penetrating protons that are not correctly identified as penetrating. The influence of this population on the highest energetic channel was concluded to be negligible.

Patch 2 April 16th, 2024 proton contamination

The right subfigure of Fig. 15 shows the same measurements as in the left panel, but for the period of July to September 2022. A third population C is highlighted, which mainly spans across the highest energetic channel. This population was identified as proton contamination. This proton track was eradicated with

Figure 15: Left: Pulse Height Analysis (PHA) data of electrons stopping in C measured between March 2020 and October 2021 before the patch introducing a 1 MeV threshold in C omitting population A entries. Red lines mark the borders of the channels. See Fig. 4 in [Fleth et al. \(2023\)](#) for further detail. **Right:** Same for measurements between July and September 2022. Marked as red C is a population of protons contaminating mainly the highest energy channel.

the second major patch of April 16, 2024, by demanding that neither signal in the A / B detectors be > 500 keV.

All events identified prior to the second patch needed to be inspected for proton contamination. Two examples are shown in Fig. 16 where PHA entries classified as contamination according to the definition of patch 2 are shown in red and regular entries due to electrons in blue. The left plot shows a small event from October 3, 2023 where an increase in the highest electron channel was detected, which can be clearly attributed to contamination. The sum of the weighted PHA counts classified as contamination adds up to 332 compared to 205 regular entries. Events with a contamination count greater than 50% of the total amount are discarded.

The plot on the right of Fig. 16 shows another example of an event that lasted from August 8 to 10, 2023. A clear proton track and therefore contamination can be seen; however, the amount of contamination makes up only $\approx 1/3$ of the total amount and therefore the event would not be considered dominated by contamination. Notable here is the culmination of regular counted PHA entries at the lower right part of the 2-D histogram, i.e., events with low-energy deposit in A + B and close to 15 MeV in the C detector.

This culmination appears to be coming from population B particles and is qualitatively investigated in Fig. 17. Two examples with a profound contribution of population B particles are given. The red dotted lines mark the nominal channel boundaries and the black boundaries are set at 2.2, 5 and 11 MeV defining new channels with sharper distinction, colored green, blue, and purple. Also shown in red are contamination entries in the original boundaries. The example given in the left plot of Fig. 17 shows a large amount of particles measured with $C > 11$ MeV whereas the overall contribution of contamination is small. The right plot shows the event of August 8 to 10, 2023 already shown in the right plot of Fig. 16. Here, the separation of population B particles from the regular electron entries would result in a majority of contamination. We conclude that the influence of population B particles has to be re-evaluated and quantified in the future. A visual inspection of all events suggests that a ratio of 3 to 1 of counts > 11 MeV in C (purple) and counts between 5 and 11 MeV (blue) qualitatively separates events strongly influenced by spillover of population B particles from clean events. As of the first release of this catalogue, all events with such a ratio exceeding 3 are flagged in the comments and should be considered with care until better measures to quantify the influence of population B particles have been established.

Figure 16: Two examples of contamination in the highest electron channel of HET. Shown in red are PHA values with energy deposited > 500 keV in either A or B counted as negative counts. Shown in blue are nominal counts in this channel as after the patch of April 16th, 2024. **Left:** clear example of a time period dominated by protons. **Right:** Ambiguous event with some contamination and apparent contribution of population B protons.

Figure 17: Qualitative examination of contamination due to population B protons for two different time periods. The red dotted lines mark the nominal channel boundaries and the black boundaries are set at 2.2, 5 and 11 MeV defining new channels with sharper distinction colored green, blue and purple. Also shown in red are contamination entries in the original boundaries. The colored numbers give the sum of the weighted counts for each channel.

2.3 Kiel Electron Telescope (KET)

The **KET** onboard the Ulysses spacecraft is part of the Ulysses COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation (**COSPIN**) and was designed to study energetic charged particles in interplanetary space. Its primary objectives include measuring the energy spectra of electrons, protons, and helium across a wide energy range. The main objective was to measure the electron fluxes between a few MeV and below several GeV (for details see [Simpson et al. 1992](#)). To allow charge-sign-dependent studies on the solar modulation of **GCR**, it also provided measurements of proton and helium fluxes in several energy windows between a few MeV and above 2 GeV/amu (see studies of electrons and protons at a rigidity of about 2.5 GV by [Rastoin et al. 1996](#); [Ferrando et al. 1996](#); [Heber et al. 2002a, 2003a, 2009](#)).

2.3.1 Sensor description

The detector system, illustrated in Fig. 18, consists of two main components:

The entrance telescope combines a Cherenkov detector made of silica-aerogel (C1 in Fig. 18) positioned between two semiconductor detectors (D1 and D2). Together with the guard counter (A), this configuration defines the geometry of the system and selects particles with velocities exceeding $\beta > 0.938$.

The calorimeter (C2) is a lead-fluoride (PbF₂) crystal with a thickness of 2.5 radiation lengths, which functions as a Cherenkov detector where electron showers develop. C2 is surrounded by an anti-coincidence to reject particles that penetrate C2 not within the opening angle defined by the entrance telescope. Lastly, a scintillator (S2) detects particles, i.e. electrons that are not absorbed by C2.

Figure 18: Sketch of the KET: Cherenkov detectors C1 and C2, silicon SSDs D1 and D2 and scintillation detectors S1, S2 and anti-coincidence are shown as well as the photomultipliers detecting photons emitted in the Cherenkov and scintillation detectors (Fig. 5.3 from [Dunzlaff \(2012\)](#)).

Channel	Type	MeV/nuc	Coincidence condition	Priority
P1	Proton	2.7 - 5.4	D11 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	
	Proton	23.1 - 34.1		
	Alpha	2.3 - 2.7		
P4	Proton	5.4 - 23.1	D12 D13 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	
	Alpha	2.7 - 6.0		
	Alpha	20.4 - 34.2		
P32	Proton	34.1 - 116	D11 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	1
P116	Proton	116 - 190	D10 D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	1
	Alpha	126 - 190		
P190	Proton	190 - 1880	D10 D11 C10 D20 D21 C20 C21 S20 A0	0
P4000	Proton	> 1880	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 C21 S20 A0	0
A4	Alpha	6.0 - 20.4	D13 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0	1
A32	Alpha	34.2 - 116	D12 D13 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	
A116	Alpha	116 - 126	D12 D13 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	
A190	Alpha	190 - 1880	D11 D12 C10 D21 C20 S20 A0	
A4000	Alpha	> 1880	D11 D12 C10 C11 D21 C20 S20 A0	
E4	Electron	4 - 9	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 S20 A0	
E12	Electron	9 - 170	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C20 S20 A0	3
E300	Electron	> 170	D10 D11 C10 C11 D20 D21 C21 S20 A0	2

Table 3: KET channels description

2.3.2 KET electron measurements

Three electron channels are defined based on the detector responses, with the shared criterion that a Cerenkov signal is observed in C1 and no particles trigger the anti-coincidence detector:

The lowest energy channel, E4, corresponds to electrons entering D1 and stopping either in D2 or at the top of C2, resulting in no signals in C2 or S2. These electrons have energies ranging from 4 to 12 MeV. Data from this channel have been used to analyse Jovian electrons (Ferrando et al. 1993b,a; Heber et al. 2002b, 2003b; Dunzlaff et al. 2010; Dunzlaff 2012; Dunzlaff et al. 2013)

The highest-energy electron channel, E300, is defined by particles penetrating the KET leading to signals in all detectors. Depending on the amplitude of the C2 signal, electrons escaping C2 and triggering S2 are classified in either the high-energy proton channel or the highest-energy electron channel.

The middle energy channel, E12, which will be the focus in this study, is associated with electrons that produce a significant shower in C2 without any charged particles detected in S2. This channel covers an energy range of approximately 10 to above 170 MeV. The higher the energy, the more profound the shower in the calorimeter C2 gets, which allows to extract information on the particle energy.

In addition to information about the type and energy range of the incoming particle using coincidence-anticoincidence logic, the pulse height is determined in each detector. The memory reserved for PHA allows 20 events to be stored per cycle. With Ulysses as a spinning probe, one cycle is given in multiples of 10 revolutions, depending on the availability of the telemetry. At 5 revolutions per minute, the best possible information transfer is therefore 20 PHA events per 120 seconds. In the event that 20 events have already been evaluated before the end of a cycle, the option to overwrite one of the last 10 events based on priority has been implemented. The E12 has the highest priority, ensuring that in the event of an SEE-event, the data is always available.

The left panel of Fig.19 shows the mean response of the photomultiplier 2, measuring the Cerenkov

Figure 19: Left: mean C2 response for electron calibration measurements (black) and obtained from [GEANT-4](#) simulations (blue). **Right:** mean C2 response of the simulation converted to PHA. Black dotted horizontal lines mark PHA values of 80, 90, 100 and 110.

light emission of the C2, as a function of energy. The black crosses mark calibration measurements performed at accelerators in Bonn and L'Orme des Merisiers (for details see [Sierks 1988](#)), while the blue curve shows the results of [GEANT-4](#) beam simulations performed in the scope of [D2.5](#) in good agreement with the calibration measurements. The right panel shows the same simulations converted to [PHA](#) values as a function of energy. The dotted horizontal lines mark [PHA](#) values of 80, 90, 100 and 110 representing the sub-channel limits used for the event identification (see [Fig.23](#)). It should be noted that while the sub-channels intersect at ≈ 15 -30 MeV for accelerator beams, these sub-channels more closely represent ≈ 10 -20 MeV electrons for an isotropic radiation environment depending on the spectral index.

3 Methodology

3.1 Event detection and onset-time determination

Detecting the onset of Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events is crucial for timing analysis and for identifying the solar drivers of the resulting events. Various methodologies have been applied in the literature to identify SEP initiation, including statistical, empirical, and Machine Learning (ML) approaches. In particular, methods that have been extensively used by the scientific community include the:

1. **Poisson Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) method:** a statistical tool designed to detect shifts in processes where events occur randomly over time, following a Poisson distribution (see details and references in [Palmroos et al. 2022](#)).
2. **n- σ method:** a statistical approach used to determine the onset time of an SEP event by identifying when a signal deviates significantly from its baseline or background level (see e.g. [Papaioannou et al. 2014](#)).
3. **linear fits:** an empirical method, employing a linear fit which is applied to the log-values of SEP intensities at the start of the event. The intersection of the fit with the pre-event background is used for determining the onset time (see e.g. [Posner et al. 2024](#)).
4. **Machine Learning:** ML models have been used to identify the start of an SEP event. Such techniques include Time Series Forest (TSF), Supervised Time Series Forest (STSF), and Bag of SFA Symbols (BOSS) that utilize multivariate time series data from proton channels and X-ray flux measurements ([Rotti et al. 2024](#)).

3.1.1 Method of choice

The **3- σ Method** is the method of choice for this deliverable, as it is the most easily applicable method for all data sets. It establishes a detection threshold based on the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of pre-event background measurements: Figure 20 displays an example for our method:

Figure 20: Illustration for the methodology used to determine the SEE onset, the maximum and fluence using the February 25, 2014 SEP event. The right panel differs from the left one by using only time periods after the X4.9 solar flare (see [Sharykin et al. 2023](#), and references therein). The periods that determine the background flux and the fluence are marked by gray and green shading, respectively. The red, blue, and green points mark the time of the onset determined by the 3- σ method and by eye as well as the maximum flux, respectively. The red horizontal line marks the 3- σ level determined from the background interval and the green horizontal line marks the 1/2 peak flux level. For details see text.

Background period: A quiet time period prior to the **SEP** event, where no significant enhancements in particle flux occur, is chosen by the user. This is indicated by the gray shaded period in Fig. 20. The mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the particle flux during this period are computed.

Threshold Definition The detection threshold is defined as:

$$F_{\text{thresh}} = \mu + 3\sigma \quad (8)$$

Any observed flux (F) that exceeds this threshold is considered a candidate for an SEP onset. The 3- σ -flux is shown in the figure by the dashed red line.

Event Detection The SEP event is identified if the flux exceeds the threshold for a predefined duration, typically for three consecutive time bins. In the case shown in the figure the onset is found during the preceding X-ray flare discussed by Sharykin et al. (2023) (see left panel of Fig. 20). If the particle onset is well separated from the maximum in the X-ray flux, the background period can be chosen on the cost of statistics differently. This is shown in the right panel. The corresponding onset times are 2014-02-25 00:44:00 and 2014-02-25 02:16:00, respectively. Note that the onset found for the X-ray peak corresponds well with the one of the HXR-flux determined in Sharykin et al. (2023). Not shown here are cases for which the decay of the X-ray flux overlaps with the onset of the electron event. In these cases the onset time has to be determined by eye. The corresponding times are marked by the blue points in the figure. The onset time of 2014-02-25 02:30:00 for the electron onset is later due to the fact that the 3- σ level was higher in the left panel. In the catalogue both the 3- σ as well as the eye-ball onset are given for each event.

3.2 SEP peak flux and fluence

SEP events are characterized by the rapid acceleration of particles to high energies. Two key parameters used to characterize **SEP** events are the maximum flux and the fluence. Here we outline common methodologies for their determination.

3.2.1 Determination of maximum intensity:

The maximum intensity, often denoted as Φ_{max} , is the peak value of the particle intensity during the event. Common methodologies include:

Direct Peak Flux Measurement: The simplest approach is to identify the maximum value of the time-dependent particle flux $\Phi(t)$:

$$\Phi_{\text{max}} = \max\{\Phi(t)\}, \quad (9)$$

where $\Phi(t)$ is obtained from in situ spacecraft measurements (Cane et al. 2003).

Smoothing and Peak Finding Algorithms: Since **SEP** event profiles can be noisy, smoothing algorithms such as moving averages or Savitzky-Golay filters are often applied before determining Φ_{max} (Reames 1999).

Fitting Analytical Functions: **SEP** time profiles can be modeled using empirical functions, such as an exponential rise and decay model:

$$\Phi(t) = \Phi_0 e^{-t/\tau}, \quad (10)$$

where fitting parameters I_0 and τ are obtained through least-squares fitting (Vainio et al. 2013).

Unfortunately, in this analysis we cannot use any of the above methods because of reasons laid out in the following. As an example, the electron flux time profile shown in Fig. 20 has an additional

maximum on early February 26, 2014, during an X-ray flare observed by **RHESSI** (<https://hesperia.gsfc.nasa.gov/rhessi3/data-access/rhessi-data/flare-list/>). Thus the first method would give the maximum of the second flare, while the second method would depend on the smoothing period. The third method can also not be applied because of the jump in the time profile that is caused by the ring switch of the instrument. Thus, we decided to determine the maximum flux manually by eye.

3.2.2 Determination of Fluences

The fluence, F , represents the total particle exposure over the event duration and is given by:

$$F = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \Phi(t) dt. \quad (11)$$

Several methods can be used to evaluate this integral.

Numerical Integration: For discrete time series data, numerical integration techniques such as the trapezoidal rule are used:

$$F \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \frac{\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{2} (t_{i+1} - t_i). \quad (12)$$

Analytical Integration of Fitted Curves: When an analytical function is used to describe $I(t)$, the fluence can be computed by integrating the function over the event duration (Tylka & Lee 2005).

Figure 21: Example of the fluence calculation from **SOHO / EPHIN**. Shown here is the time profile during the April 20, 1998 event. The red, blue, and green dots give the onset time determined by the 3σ -method and by eye as well as the maximum flux, respectively. The gray and green shaded time periods give the period used for background and fluence computation, respectively. The red horizontal line marks the 3σ level determined from the background interval and the green horizontal line marks the $1/2$ peak flux level. For details see text.

As for the determination of the maximum flux, we decided here to determine the fluence during a time profile that is given by the time period for which the flux $\Phi(t)$ is larger than $\Phi_{max}/2$. Since the interval for

which the fluence is computed can be ambiguous, it is given in the catalogue, too. An example of this, the **SEP** event on April 20, 1998 is shown in Fig. 21.

The red, blue, and green dots give the onset time determined by the $3\text{-}\sigma$ method and by eye as well as the maximum flux, respectively. The gray and green shaded time periods give the period used for background and fluence computation, respectively. To determine the time period for which we compute the fluence, we follow the procedure discussed in [Jiggins et al. \(2018\)](#): We first determine the maximum flux Φ_{max} and then time periods when the flux $\Phi(t)$ becomes smaller than $\Phi_{max}/2$ to obtain the limits. Due to statistical fluctuation or the onset of a new **SEP** event, the start and end times are chosen by eye. Thus in all entries of the catalogue the time of and the peak flux Φ_{max} together with the fluence and time period we used for the fluence computation are given.

The determination of the onset time, the maximum intensity, and the fluence in SEP events is crucial for understanding particle acceleration and transport processes. Here we use the $3\text{-}\sigma$ -method with a background time period given by the user. The time of Φ_{max} is determined by the user and the fluence is calculated based on the time interval that the Φ_{max} drops to $\Phi_{max}/2$.

4 Catalogues

The first versions of all catalogues are currently only available within the project and can be assessed via the internal repository of SPEARHEAD at:

1. **SOHO/EPHIN (~5 MeV)**: <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/XWEQGmkmKLDCY4R>
2. **SolO/HET (~1 MeV)**: <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/Y4KGN7cXRiAeALo>
3. **SolO/HET (≥ 5 MeV)**: <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/RmdxRMPxgfPqsm>
4. **Ulysses/KET (5 MeV)**: <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/6gRxZFcqsJt69Dq>

All catalogues will be provided through a public repository (i.e., SPEARHEAD's Zenodo Community) at a later stage, providing the SPEARHEAD consortium with time to further explore the science that will be extracted by the catalogues in due time within the project. The absence of an entry in a row or column in any of these catalogues indicates that we could not calculate the relevant parameter, the result was not meaningful, or that there was a data gap.

4.1 Description of information provided by all catalogues

This section outlines the descriptions of the catalogues, including the columns and information provided to users. Effort has been made to ensure that all SPEARHEAD catalogues deliver outputs in a consistent format, facilitating seamless integration for further usage and exploitation. In particular, Columns A and B provide the numbering of the event and its identifier, columns C, D and E provide the start and end time of the background period prior to the event and its period-averaged flux, column F and G give the onset of the **SEE** event determined by the 3σ -method and by eye, column H and I give the time of maximum and the maximum flux, J to L contain the period (start and end time) for which the fluence has been computed. In column M we give further comments.

In detail, the catalogue is structured as follows:

- Columns A and B: number and identification of the event
 - Column A:** Number in the catalogue
 - Column B:** Identifier: for **EPHIN** and **SolO** a link to the > 100 MeV protons catalogue by [Vainio et al. \(2024\)](#) is provided if the event is listed there.
- Columns C to I: Instrument data information
 - Column C:** Efficient energy determined by bow-tie analysis for times including the maximum period.
 - Column D:** Begin of the period for which we determined the background flux. The format is %Y-%m-%d %H:%M".
 - Column E:** End of the period for which we determined the background flux. The format is %Y-%m-%d %H:%M".
 - Column F:** Mean background flux of the channel ($1/(\text{s cm}^2 \text{ sr MeV})$). Note, for **KET** the values are given as counts/second.
 - Column G:** Onset time determined by the 3σ -method. Note, for **KET** the time is given by analyzing Ulysses **HET**.
 - Column H:** Onset time determined by eye
 - Column I:** Time of peak flux

Column J: Peak flux of the event [$1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr s MeV})$] Note, for **KET** the countrate of subchannel $100 < C2 \leq 110$ is given

Column K: Begin of the period for which we determined the fluence. The format is %Y-%m-%d %H:%M".

Column L: End of the period for which we determined the fluence. The format is %Y-%m-%d %H:%M".

Column M: Fluence of the event [$1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr MeV})$]. Note, for **KET** the **PHA** statistics determine the time period.

- Column N - P: spacecraft location (Stoneyhurst) from <https://solar-mach.github.io>

Column N: radial distance in AU from the Sun

Column O: spacecraft longitude

Column P: spacecraft latitude

Column Q: Any other comments

4.2 SOHO/EPHIN ~ 5 MeV catalogue description

We utilized in the first step of creating this catalogue the SPEARHEAD D5.1 > 100 MeV proton list (Vainio et al. 2024). For this purpose, we scanned EPHIN well curated and corrected data at ~ 5 MeV. From 1997 to 2017 a total of 135 SEE events were identified. Since SEP electron events have to be distinguished from Jovian electron events, in the final list, we will further incorporate the event list of ≈ 30 MeV protons by Miteva et al. (2024). This will clear out any Jovian electron enhancements if present. The solar associations of the identified SEP events are given in D4.2 of SPEARHEAD (see Rouillard et al. 2024). The 135 events are provided in the format according to Sec. 4.1 at <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/XWEQGmkmKLDCY4R>.

4.3 SolO/HET ~ 1 MeV catalogue description

We surveyed in situ measurements of ~ 10 MeV (9.18-10.98 MeV) protons and ~ 1 MeV (0.45-2.40 MeV) electrons measured by the High Energy Telescope (HET) of the Energetic Particle Detector (EPD) suite (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020) during the first \sim four years of the mission from 2020-2023. A subset of the identified SEP events reached ~ 50 MeV for protons, which are relevant for Space Weather. In addition to the identification of the events, our work utilized proton measurements by HET, covering a range from 7.04–104.9 MeV for protons distributed over 36 channels and 0.45-18.83 MeV for electrons distributed over 4 channels. In order to increase the signal to noise ratio for several channels, we combined particles in triplets of proton channels and pairs of electron channels leading to 12 proton channels and two electron ones. These combined channels were used in the Velocity Dispersion Analysis (VDA) to identify the path length traveled by the energetic particles and to estimate their possible Solar Release Time (SRT). Moreover, Time Shifting Analysis (TSA) was applied for ~ 1 MeV electrons. We finally further examined energetic particle measurements obtained from the Suprathermal Ion Spectrograph (SIS) instrument, which is also part of the EPD suite on board the Solar Orbiter spacecraft and observes the elemental and isotopic composition of ions in the energy range of ~ 100 keV nuc^{-1} to ~ 10 MeV nuc^{-1} .

4.3.1 Selection criteria

We scanned the Solar Orbiter HET data from February 2020 to the end of August 2023, during the ascending phase of solar cycle 25. During this interval Solar Orbiter completed five orbits around the Sun and spanned radial distances from 0.28 to 0.99 au. Panels (a) and (b) of Fig. 22 show six-hour

averages of the HET proton and electron intensities, respectively, recorded during this interval. The vertical magenta lines depict the SEP events that were identified and catalogued in this study. Panel (c) of Fig. 22 indicates the heliocentric distance of Solar Orbiter and panel (d) shows the evolution of the solar cycle using the daily and monthly-averaged (thick line) sunspot number³.

Figure 22: Solar Orbiter data used in the scanning and the creation of the catalog. Six-hour averages of HET (a) protons at ~ 10 MeV and (b) electrons at ~ 1 MeV; (c) presents the heliocentric distance of Solar Orbiter; (d) shows the evolution of the solar cycle based on daily (monthly) averages of the sunspot number, indicated with a grey (black) line. The identified SEP events are marked with the vertical magenta lines.

The following criteria were applied for the identification of the SEP events in both protons and near-relativistic electrons: (1) the event had a clear increase above background in the near-relativistic electrons (at ~ 1 MeV; 0.45-2.40 MeV) and (2) it was associated with an increase in the ~ 10 MeV (9.18-10.98 MeV) proton recordings. Intensity-time plots of higher energy (~ 50 MeV) protons were also scanned⁴. As can be seen in Fig. 22(b) there is an upward shift in the background level of the electrons from $\sim 4 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to 10^{-1} [e/cm²/sr/s/MeV] from 12-10-2021 onwards. This is due to an update in the absolute threshold in the C detector of the HET instrument, details are given in figure 5 by Fleth et al. (2023). As evident in Fig. 22 (a) and (b), the selected SEP events of the entire catalog present a clear enhancement of electron intensities above their background level, as identified above. A total of 75 SEP events were identified, about half of which (36 events or 48%) present an enhancement in the flux of ~ 50 MeV protons. The current version of the catalog ends in August 2023.

For the identified SEP events, we obtained the peak intensity (in units of [particles/cm² sr s MeV]) for both protons (~ 10 MeV) and electrons (~ 1 MeV) of the prompt component, namely the peak before arrival of an in-situ shock (if present) based on 10 minute averages, similar to Lario & Karelitz (2014). Therefore, particle enhancements commonly associated with the arrival of an IP shock (if any) at the spacecraft (i.e., the energetic storm particles –ESP– component) are excluded (Papaioannou et al. 2023;

³Source: WDC-SILSO, Royal Observatory of Belgium, Brussels; <https://www.sidc.be/SILSO/datafiles>

⁴The SEP events that reached high energies (above 50 MeV) were marked with a Y/N index in the catalogue

Rodríguez-García et al. 2023, and details therein). Additionally, we computed the time-integrated fluences (in units of particles / cm² sr MeV) by integrating the intensity in each channel throughout the SEP event (Papaioannou et al. 2023). These values are given in the list of the 75 SEP events selected from this survey. One important remark has to do with the calculated peak fluxes and fluences for the events identified prior to the update in the absolute threshold in the C detector of HET (i.e., 12-10-2021). It affects in total the first 18 (out of the 75) SEP events, and for this release a comment has been added in the catalogue, notifying the end user. Since August 2023 another 50 events have been identified following the same methodology. The calculations for the SEP characteristics and the relation to solar sources are in progress. The catalogue is currently provided online as a .xlsx-file via <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/Y4KGN7cXRiAeALo> and is planned to be a living list, namely to be updated on a regular basis. The solar associations for this (and the following catalogue) will be incorporated in an update of D4.2 (Rouillard et al. 2024).

4.4 SoI/HET ≥ 5 MeV catalogue description

The highest electron channel of SoI/HET measuring 5.7 - 15.3 MeV electrons (Fleth et al. 2023) was scanned for enhancements beginning at the launch of the mission in February 2020 until 2025. The basis of the scanning was the initial catalogue from ~ 1 MeV SoI/HET (Sec. 4.1). Initially 43 clear enhancements in the time profiles could be determined. Of these enhancements, 12 could be attributed to proton contamination as described in 2.2.2. The remaining 31 events are provided in the format according to Sec. 4.1 at <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/RmdxRMPxgfPqsm>.

Figure 23: Event identification for Ulysses/KET. **Left panel:** KET electron measurements in three sub-channels of the E12 coincidence channel. **Right panel:** Ulysses/HET 5-10 MeV electron countrates used for precise onset determination. The 3σ onsets for all channels are marked by stars for each channel.

4.5 KET catalogue description

4.5.1 Event identification

To find Solar Energetic Electron (SEE) events in the KET data, six-hour averaged data of electron count rates in the E12 channel are analyzed (see subsection 2.3.2). By searching for significant increases in three sub-channels ($80 < C2 \leq 90$, $90 < C2 \leq 100$, and $100 < C2 \leq 110$, respectively), periods of high electron count rates are identified. The method is visualized in the left panel of Fig. 23 for the event on August 16 in 2001. The count rate of the three subchannels is required to exceed 3σ above the mean count rate in the seven days before. If this condition is fulfilled in each of the three subchannels, the event is a potential candidate for an SEE event.

Figure 24: Temporal and spatial occurrences of 13 SEE events measured by KET.

Many of these candidates, however, are not due to solar electrons, but rather due to Jovian electrons detected during the Jupiter flybys. The first flyby was in February 1992 when Jovian gravity was used to leave the ecliptic. During a second, more distant Jupiter flyby, Jovian electrons were detected by the KET in late 2003 and throughout 2004 (Dunzlaff 2012). In the left panel of Fig. 2, an increase in electron count rates can be seen during these periods while the proton channel is not affected. Increases in electron count rates due to Solar events are accompanied by strong increases in the P32 proton count rates (Fig. 2, right panel). Therefore, the P32 proton channel is required to exceed the threshold similarly to the three electron sub-channels. To determine a more precise onset time, the electron count rates measured with Ulysses/HET are analysed. The instrument is designed to identify energy, mass and charge of cosmic rays but also measures electrons of a few MeV (Simpson et al. 1992). Due to the large geometric factor, it offers good statistics and allows an accurate determination of the onset time. For this purpose, the 10 minute averaged count rate of 5-10 MeV electrons is investigated. The process is similar to the event

identification with **KET** electron measurements as shown in the right panel of Fig. 23. The **HET** count rates are required to exceed the 3σ level of the 48h background prior to the event for three consecutive times, yielding an event onset at 05:30.

4.5.2 Ulysses/**KET** Catalogue content

During the whole mission lifetime from late 1990 until 2009, 13 clear **SEE** events with electron energies exceeding 20 MeV could be identified. The temporal and spatial occurrences of these events are displayed in Fig. 24. It can be seen that most of the events occur around the times of solar maximum of solar cycle 22 and 23 in 1991 and 2001, respectively. The events were measured at latitudes ranging from -72° up to 78° , **providing a unique perspective on the highest energetic solar electron events ever recorded**. The identified SEE events are provided in the format according to Sec. 4.1 at <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/6gRxZFcqsJt69Dq>. The solar associations will be detailed in the upcoming update of D4.2 (Rouillard et al. 2024).

5 Conclusions and Outlook

In this document, multiple catalogues of [SEE](#) events at electron energies ≥ 1 reaching beyond 10 MeV have been compiled and presented, demonstrating results from the first 15 months of the SPEARHEAD project. The first release of these electron event catalogues is based on the scanning of [SOHO / EPHIN](#), [SolO / HET](#) and Ulysses [KET](#) measurements. Therefore, the first SPEARHEAD electron catalogues provide a broad overview of (very) high energy [SEE](#) events, directly addressing the second **Science Question - SQ** put forth by the project, namely:

- **SQ2: What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?**

1. The first release of the [SOHO / EPHIN](#) catalogue is based on the catalogue provided by SPEARHEAD's D5.1 [Vainio et al. \(2024\)](#). Due to the limited period until October 2017, a total of 135 SEE events were identified. Due to the fact that both Jovian electron increases and [SEE](#) events can be the source of several-MeV electrons, the increase in the flux of protons at energies of about 30 MeV was used to separate between the sources of electron increases ([Miteva et al. 2024](#); [Vainio et al. 2024](#)).
2. The distinction from Jovian electron increases was also crucial in the compilation of the catalogue of Ulysses/[KET](#) because of its close encounter with Jupiter. A total of 13 electron events with energies above 20 MeV were found which provides unprecedented measurements as the progress in [D2.5](#) will allow spectral analysis up to 100 MeV.
3. For [SolO/HET](#), two catalogues are provided that exploit measurements at ~ 1 MeV and 5.7 - 15.3 MeV which include 75 (125) and 31 events, respectively. The distinction between highly and ultra-relativistic SEE electron events aims to address the second part of the first **SQ** by the project:

- **SQ1: How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?**

This first release of the catalogues constitutes **Deliverable D5.2** of the project. Further releases will include more events observed in the active phase of solar cycle 25 as well as revised data on the present events, where needed.

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